

SELF-REGULATED LEARNING AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF PATNA

Vinay Kumar
Dr. Vikramjit Singh

Abstract

Learning environment is very important for one's learning. When a learner understands and controls his/her learning environment, it is called Self-Regulated Learning. Good academic achievement and other aspects of a learner are supported by the ability of self-regulated learning skills. The study deals with Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) skills of students of secondary schools of Patna. The objectives of the study is to find significant difference among SRL skills of students of secondary schools of Patna on the basis of gender, medium of instruction, types of board of studies and types of schools. Purposefully 198 students of 9th standard of government, private and missionary secondary schools of Patna were selected as sample. Survey method was used in this study. Tools on Self-Regulated Learning scale designed and developed by Dr. Madhu Gupta & Ms. Dimple Mehtani (2017) was used for collecting the data from the sample. For analysis of data t-ratio and ANOVA or F-ratio has been used. The result showed significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of types of school and types of board of studies. However no significant difference was found in SRL skills on the basis of medium of instruction and gender of students of secondary schools of Patna.

Key words: Self-Regulated Learning, gender, types of schools, types of board of studies.

INTRODUCTION

“Education is the manifestation of perfection present already in man.”- Swami Vivekananda. Education helps human beings to increase and develop their thinking, reasoning, problem solving, creativity, intelligence, aptitude, sentiments, skills, good values and attitude. Through educated man is transformed into a social, moral, and spiritual human being. Proper education will teach students to

understand the different environment situation and to adjust with environment like – social environment and learning environment. Learning environment has both a direct and indirect influence on student learning, including their engagement in what is being taught, their motivation to learn and their sense of well being, belonging and personal safety. One's learning environment is very important. Self-regulated learning is one's ability to understand and control one's learning environment. Self-regulation abilities include goal setting, self-monitoring, self-instruction, and self-reinforcement (Harris & Graham, 1999). Self-regulation refers to 'thoughts, feelings and actions that are planned and adapted to the attainment of personal goals' (Zimmerman, 2000). Self-regulated learning includes: setting goals for learning, concentrating on instruction, using effective strategies to organize ideas, using resources effectively, monitoring performance, managing time effectively and holding positive beliefs about one's capabilities (Schunk and Ertmer, 2000). The present study deals with Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) skills on the basis of gender (boys and girls), medium of instruction (Hindi and English medium), types of schools(government, private & missionary) and types of board of studies (BSEB, CBSE & ICSE) of students of secondary schools of Patna. The nature of the study is descriptive and researcher has used survey method to collect data from the population which includes 9th standard students of secondary schools of Patna.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Patna of Bihar is one of the fastest developing cities in India. Patna is educational hub of Bihar and education has been very expensive here. Today we are living in such world where knowledge is widely available for free of cost on internet or other sources of knowledge which is accessible to anyone, anywhere and anytime. But it all depends on interest, attitude and self-regulating skills of a learner, how much he/she self-regulate their learning to access knowledge and achieve the success. The researcher has observed that Students of secondary schools of Patna fail to make themselves aware of their own learning and thinking process. They fail to reflect and evaluate their own strengths and weaknesses and making strategies about

learning for best outcomes. Even sometimes they fail to fix their learning aims and actual area of interest of study. So these problems lead to low achievement and other failures. The findings of the study may help students, teachers, parents and school administration to understand SRL skills. It may help stakeholders and teachers to work as good facilitators and guides and to understand the SRL skills of their students so that they may arrange instructional strategies accordingly.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study is done to assess the level of SRL skills and it also studies significant difference on the basis of gender, types of school, type of boards of studies and medium of instruction of secondary school (9th) students of Patna. Thus the title of the study is “Self-Regulated Learning among secondary school students of Patna”.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

Self- Regulated Learning (SRL) – In this study Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) skills means assessing students in six dimensions - 1. Self-awareness, 2. Planning and goal setting, 3. Self-evaluation, 4. Self-control, 5. Self-motivation and 6. Self-modification of secondary school (9th standard) students of Patna.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the significant difference in Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) study on the basis of gender (boys and girls) of secondary school students of Patna.
2. To study the significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of types of school (government, private & missionary) of secondary school students of Patna.
3. To study the significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of boards of studies (BSEB, CBSE & ICSE) of secondary school students of Patna.
4. To study the significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of medium (Hindi and English) of instruction of secondary

school students of Patna.

TOOL USED

The tool on Self-Regulated Learning scale designed and developed by Dr. Madhu Gupta & Ms. Dimple Mehtani (2017) was used for collecting the required data.

METHOD USED

For the present study, the investigator selected the survey method in the view of the objectives of the study and the nature of the problem concerned.

POPULATION

The population of the study consists of 9th Std. school students of Patna.

SAMPLE

The investigator has used purposive sampling as sampling technique and selected four schools of Patna from where he selected 198 students of 9th standard as his sample. The number of students collected from Srichandra High School, St. Michaels High School, Hartman High School, St. Paul's High School were 49, 60, 41, 48 respectively. The types of schools selected as sample are government, private and missionary school with different boards of studies BSEB, CBSE, and ICSE Board.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Depending upon the nature of the hypothesis of the investigator used the following statistical techniques: Mean, SD, t-test and ANOVA for analyzing and interpreting the data.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Only 198 students of secondary school have been taken as

- sample.
2. Only 9th standard students of secondary schools have been taken in the study.
 3. The study has been conducted in four schools of only urban area of Patna.

NULL HYPOTHESIS

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS 1

H_{0,1} There is no significant difference in self-regulated learning (SRL) skills on the basis of gender (boys and girls) of secondary school students of Patna.

To test the above hypothesis the data were collected on Self-regulated learning (SRL) skills of secondary school students of Patna. The data were analyzed using 't' statistical test. The mean scores of boys and girls in SRL skills, Standard Deviation as well as 't' value have been shown in the table-1 below.

Table-1
Self-regulated learning (SRL) skills on the basis of gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-ratio	Remark
Boys	109	174.73	18.032	1.175	NS
Girls	89	177.72	17.474		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value is 1.98)

The observation of the findings of t-test result as shown in the table-1 shows that the calculated 't' value is 1.175. When this obtained value is compared with the critical ratio value at 0.05 level (1.98) for 196 df it is found to be less and thus the difference in the mean scores is not significant and null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore it can be stated that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of SRL skills between the boys and girls of secondary schools of Patna.

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS 2

$H_{0,2}$ There is no significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of types of school (government, private & missionary) of secondary school students of Patna.

The test of above hypothesis has been done using the ANOVA technique. The mean scores on SRL skills on the basis of types of school (government, private & missionary), their SD and the F-ratio analysis results has been summarized in the table-2 (a) & 2 (b).

Table-2 Results of F-test on Self-regulated learning (SRL) skills on the basis of types of school (government, private & missionary).

**Table -2 (a)
 Descriptive of SRL skills on the basis of types of school**

Descriptive			
Types of school	N	MEAN	SD
Govt. School	49	177.12	19.170
Private School	48	169.15	16.485
Missionary School	101	178.86	16.991
Total	198	176.08	17.801

**Table -2 (b)
 ANOVA results of SRL skills on the basis of types of school**

ANOVA Result						
Groups	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F-ratio	Sig.	Remark
Between groups	3142.560	2	1571.280	5.169	.006	S**
Within groups	59279.304	195	303.996			
Total	62421.864	197				

(S** means significant at 0.01 level)

The results as can be seen in the above table-2(b) show that the calculated F-ratio is 5.169 which is more than the F-table value at 0.01 level for (2,195) df. Thus the formulated hypothesis is rejected and it can be said that there is significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of types of school (government, private & missionary) of secondary school students of Patna.

Further as the difference was found to be significant the researcher has conducted Post Hoc analysis and the result has been shown in the table -2 (c).

Table 2 (c)
Post Hoc analysis for Multiple Comparisons
among types of schools

(I) types of school:G1,P2,M3	(J) types of school:G1,P2,M3			
		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Government Schools	Private Schools	7.977	3.541	.065
	Missionary Schools	-1.739	3.035	.835
Private Schools	Government Schools	-7.977	3.541	.065
	Missionary Schools	-9.716**	3.057	.005
Missionary Schools	Government Schools	1.739	3.035	.835
	Private Schools	9.716**	3.057	.005
(** The mean difference is significant at the 0.01 level)				

The above table -2(c) reveals that the significant difference existed between the SRL skills of students of Private School and Missionary Schools at 0.01 level of significant.

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS 3

$H_{0.3}$ There is no significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of

boards of studies (BSEB, CBSE & ICSE) of secondary school students of Patna.

The test of above hypothesis has been done using the ANOVA. The mean scores on SRL skills on the basis of types of board of studies (BSEB, CBSE & ICSE), their SD and the F-ratio results has been summarized in the table 3 (a) & 3 (b) below.

Table -3 Results of F-test on Self-regulated learning (SRL) skills on the basis of types of board (BSEB, CBSE & ICSE)

**Table -3 (a)
 Descriptive on SRL skills on the basis of types of board**

Descriptive			
Types of board	N	Mean	SD
BSEB	90	177.82	1.949
CBSE	60	179.00	2.135
ICSE	48	169.15	2.379
Total	198	176.08	17.80

**Table -3 (b)
 ANOVA results of SRL skills on the basis of types of board**

ANOVA Result						
Groups	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-ratio	Sig.	Remark
Between groups	3092.729	2	1546.364	5.083	.007	S**
Within groups	59329.135	195	304.252			
Total	62421.864	197				

(S Means difference is significant at the 0.01 level)**

The results seen in the above table shows that the calculated F-ratio

is 5.083 and it is more than the F-table value at 0.01 level for (2,195) df. Thus the formulated hypothesis is rejected and it can be said that there is significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of types of board (BSEB, CBSE & ICSE) of secondary school students of Patna.

Further as the difference was found to be significant the researcher has conducted Post Hoc analysis and the result has been shown in the table -3 (c) below.

Table -3 (c)
Post Hoc analysis for Multiple Comparisons
among types of board of studies

(I) board:BSEB1,CB SE2,ICSE3	(J) board:BSEB1,CB SE2,ICSE3			
		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
BSEB	CBSE	-1.178	2.907	.914
	ICSE	8.676**	3.118	.016
CBSE	BSEB	1.178	2.907	.914
	ICSE	9.854**	3.378	.011
ICSE	BSEB	-8.676**	3.118	.016
	CBSE	-9.854**	3.378	.011
(** The mean difference is significant at the 0.01 level)				

The above table reveals that the significant difference existed between the SRL skills of students of BSEB board and ICSE board at 0.01 level also there is significant difference between the SRL skills of students of ICSE board and CBSE board.

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS 4

H_{0.4} There is no significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of medium (Hindi and English) of instruction of secondary school

students of Patna.

To test the above hypothesis the collected data on Self-regulated learning (SRL) skills on the basis of medium (Hindi, English) of instruction of secondary school students of Patna were analyzed using 't' statistical test. The mean scores of SRL skills on the basis of medium of instruction, standard deviation as well as t-test value has been shown in the table 4 below.

Table -4
Self-regulated learning (SRL) skills on the basis
of medium of instruction

Medium	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	Remark
Hindi	90	177.82	18.487	1.262	Not significant
English	108	174.62	17.158		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value is 1.98)

It is inferred from the above table- 4 that the mean value of Hindi medium students (177.82) is greater than the mean value of English medium students (174.62). The observation of the findings of t-test as it is seen that the calculated 't' value is 1.262. When this obtained value is compared with the critical ratio value at 0.05 level (1.98) for 196 df it is found to be less and thus the difference in the mean scores is not significant and thus null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore it can be stated that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of SRL skills on the basis of medium (Hindi, English) of instruction of secondary school students of Patna.

INTERPRETATION OF THE FINDINGS

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of SRL skills between boys and girls students of secondary schools of Patna. It may be due to the fact that a skill can be mastered by anybody. It all depends on the practice. Similarly, the level of SRL skills do not depend upon the gender but it depends upon the

practice of the skill by the individual.

2. There is significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of types of school (government, private & missionary) of students of secondary schools of Patna. It was found that the significant difference lied in SRL skills between Private school students and Missionary school students. It may be due to the fact that missionary school environment might be more disciplined which might help the students for self-discipline for self-study.
3. There is significant difference in SRL skills on the basis of types of board of studies (BSEB, CBSE & ICSE) of students of secondary schools of Patna. The significant difference existed in SRL skills between students of BSEB board and ICSE board students and also there is significant difference in SRL skills between students of ICSE board and CBSE board students. It may be due the fact that in BSEB board most of the students might do self-study at home and CBSE board students might get more assignments and project work based learning which might motivate students to organize their learning by themselves.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of SRL skills on the basis of medium (Hindi, English) of students of instruction of secondary school of Patna. It means that the SRL skills among students of both the mediums remained the same due to the fact that the skills have no role to play with respect to the medium of schooling.

CONCLUSION

It is found in the study that there is significant difference in SRL skills of students of secondary schools of Patna on the basis of types

of school and types of board of studies. It may be due to the fact that missionary school environment might be more disciplined which might help the students for self-discipline for self-study. Similarly, most of the students of BSEB board and CBSE board might do self-study at home. Students might be getting more assignments and project work based learning which motivated students to organize their learning by themselves. However the study showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of SRL skills students of secondary schools of Patna on the basis of medium of instruction and gender. It means that the level of SRL skills do not depend upon gender and medium of instruction but it depends upon the practice of the skill by the individual. The skills have no role to play with respect to the medium of schooling and gender. SRL skills play important role in organizing learning process, practicing self-discipline, developing good habits and making the life more effective and successful. The skills should be taught to every student in schools. Well understanding of SRL skill may help students to organize their learning, to use material like technology and library more effectively. Awareness of SRL skill may help stakeholders and English teachers to work as good facilitators and guides and to understand the SRL skill of their students so that they will arrange instructional strategies accordingly. Awareness programs on SRL skills should be organized at secondary level schools for better outcomes in all aspects of life of a learner.

REFERENCES

- Harris, K. & Graham, S. (1999). Programmatic intervention research: Illustrations from the evolution of self-regulated strategy development. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 22, 251-262.
- Zimmerman B. J. (2000). Attaining self-regulation: a social cognitive perspective, in *Handbook of Self-Regulation*, eds Boekaerts M., Pintrich P. R., Zeidner M., editors. (San Diego, CA: Academic Press;), 13-39. 10.1016/b978-012109890-2/50031-7
- Schunk, D. H., & Ertmer, P. A., (2000). Self-regulation and Academic Learning: Self- efficacy Enhancing Interventions. In M. Boekaerts, P. R. Pintrich, M. Zeidner (Eds.),

Handbook of self-regulation. San Diego, CA US: Academic Press.

(PDF) DEVELOPING DIFFERENTIATED ELECTRONIC SUPPLEMENTARY READING EXERCISE FOR THE SLOW LEARNERS OF SEVENTH YEAR STUDENTS AT SMP N 2 SINGARAJA. Available from:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335634441_DEVELOPING_DIFFERENTIATED_ELECTRONIC_SUPPLEMENTARY_READING_EXERCISE_FOR_THE_SLOW_LEARNERS_OF_SEVENTH_YEAR_STUDENTS_AT_SMP_N_2_SINGARAJA [accessed Feb 05 2019].

•••